

Table S6. Maximum sequence dissimilarity between isolates of the same *Aspergillus* species whose species limits have been delimited using methods based on multispecies coalescent model; only species represented by isolates from at least three countries were included.

Species (No. of isolates)	Maximum sequence dissimilarity between strains						Reference
	<i>benA</i>	<i>CaM</i>	<i>RPB2</i>	<i>Mcm</i> ₇	<i>Tsr1</i>	<i>Act</i>	
sect. <i>Nigri</i> ser. <i>Nigri</i>							
<i>A. brasiliensis</i> (20)	2.7	3.7	1.4	1.8 ¹	1 ¹	0.7 ¹	this study
<i>A. niger</i> (152)	1.8	2.7	1.9	0.8 ²	2.1 ²	0.8 ²	this study
<i>A. tubingensis</i> narrow ³ (81)	2.8	3.6	2.9	3.7 ⁴	0.6 ⁴	0.9 ⁴	this study
<i>A. tubingensis</i> broad ⁵ (97)	7.1	6	2.9	3.7 ⁶	3.8 ⁶	2.6 ⁶	this study
<i>A. luchuensis</i> (incl. <i>A. piperis</i>) (13)	1.8	2	0.8	1.9 ⁷	0.9 ⁷	0.9 ⁷	this study
sect. <i>Candidi</i>							
<i>A. campestris</i> (7)	2.2	4	4.3	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. candidus</i> (23)	3	1.5	1.2	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. dobrogensis</i> (22)	1.4	0.2	0.6	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. neotritici</i> (15)	2	1.6	0.8	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. pragensis</i> (8)	0	0.2	0.4	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. subalbidus</i> (29)	7.4	2.5	3.7	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. taichungensis</i> (4)	3.3	2.8	1.2	–	–	–	Glässnerová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
sect. <i>Flavipedes</i>							
<i>A. iizukae</i> (20)	4.6	3.4	0.9	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>A. micronesiensis</i> (20)	1.5	1.7	0.7	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>A. spelaeus</i> (16)	1.3	1.5	0.9	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2021)
<i>A. templicola</i> (7)	1.8	1.7	1.1	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2021)
sect. <i>Fumigati</i>							
<i>A. arcoviridensis</i> (13)	2.2	0.9	0.5	–	–	3.5	Hubka <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>A. felis</i> (35)	6.3	3.1	0.6	1.3	3.3	2.5	Hubka <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>A. pseudoviridinutans</i> (8)	3.1	2.2	1.9	0.7	1.4	2.1	Hubka <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>A. udagawae</i> (25)	1.3	2.9	1.2	–	–	4.6	Hubka <i>et al.</i> (2018)
sect. <i>Nidulantes</i>							
<i>A. creber</i> (~90)	2.3	2.2	2.8	2.7	2.4	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. falconensis</i> (8)	1.6	2.6	0.7	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2020) ⁸
<i>A. spectabilis</i> (4)	1.5	2	1	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2020)
<i>A. stella-maris</i> (4)	0	0.2	0	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2020)
<i>A. stellatus</i> (10)	2.9	1.2	1.2	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2020)
<i>A. sydowii</i> (23)	0.5	1	1	0.6	0.7	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. versicolor</i> (~90)	3.7	3.3	3.4	3.3	3.1	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>A. unguis</i> (7)	0.7	0.7	1.2	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2020)
sect. <i>Restricti</i>							
<i>A. caesiellus</i> (9)	0.5	0.7	1.3	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. conicus</i> (19)	4.9	1.5	0.7	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. destruens</i> (14)	5.9	1.5	1.5	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. domesticus</i> (8)	2.1	1.3	1.1	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. glabripes</i> (11)	2	0	1.2	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. magnivesiculatus</i> (11)	1.4	2.4	1.6	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. penicillioides</i> (26)	5	2	0.9	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. restrictus</i> (17)	2.8	0.5	2.2	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. reticulatus</i> (13)	1.4	0.2	1.2	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. tardicrescens</i> (9)	0	1.5	0.6	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)
<i>A. vitricola</i> (17)	8	4.7	2.2	–	–	–	Sklenář <i>et al.</i> (2017)

¹sequences were extracted from the whole-genome sequences analysed in this study (n = 4); see Fig. 4 and Table S3

²sequences were extracted from the whole-genome sequences analysed in this study (n = 12); see Fig. 4 and Table S3

³narrow concept of *A. tubingensis* corresponds to the variant A in Fig. 8 (*A. tubingensis* comprises *A. costaricaensis* and *A. neoniger*; the narrow concept of *A. tubingensis* would also involve *A. chiangmaiensis* and *A. pseudopiperis* but sequences of these species were excluded from comparison due to their low quality)

⁴sequences were extracted from the whole-genome sequences analysed in this study (n = 9); see Fig. 4 and Table S3

⁵broad concept of *A. tubingensis* corresponds to the variant D in Fig. 8, i.e., the whole *A. tubingensis* lineage; the sequences of *A. chiangmaiensis*, *A. pseudopiperis* and *A. pseudotubingensis* were excluded from comparison due to their low quality

⁶sequences were extracted from the whole-genome sequences analysed in this study (n = 14); see Fig. 4 and Table S3

⁷sequences of *A. luchuensis/A. piperis* were extracted from the whole-genome sequences analysed in this study (n = 3); see Fig. 4 and Table S3

⁸Sklenář F, Jurjević Ž, Peterson SW, *et al.* (2020). Increasing the species diversity in the *Aspergillus* section *Nidulantes*: six novel species mainly from the indoor environment. *Mycologia* **112**: 342–370.